

THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES AND PRINCIPLES OF STRUCTURAL ELEMENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10402279>

Abstract. *The point is that the activity of the educator, who carries out the training of prospective specialists in the field of education, special requirements are made in connection with the effective disclosure of the potential of the modern information learning environment in the process of formation of students' professional skills. In the process of professional development of students, mutual cooperation in the field of education, as well as dynamic pace of development of pedagogical information teaching environment, the pedagogue views not only the application of effective technologies, but also the interaction in the field of Education.*

Keywords: *technologies, interaction, education, professional development, professional skills, didactic skills.*

INTRODUCTION. Today, the practice of teaching related to the development of information and Communication Technology in the field of vocational education has changed significantly. The most active changes are associated with the development and introduction of new media into the educational process, the peculiarity of which is their ability:

- to organize the perception of educational information in a new way - more complex, systematic, multifaceted;
- to stimulate the cognitive interest of students, maintain the motivational area of teaching and its emotional attitude;
- Organization of self-introduction, rapid, final control of educational results.

In the learning process, teaching can help in the implementation of various teaching models including interactive learning models with the use of information tools:

- compliance with the improvement of the teaching process, modern capabilities and requirements of teaching subjects;
- develop independent work capacity;
- development of students' creative abilities;
- increase motivation on the subject under study;
- individualization of training;
- development of the ability to self-educate and further develop, etc.

We know that the formation of didactic skills is a long – term complex process, in which the stages associated with the logic of professional training (from theory to practice), the structure of pedagogical activity (from the Gnostic component - to the project), the improvement of skills (their transfer from one level to another - up) are objectively present.

Analysis of pedagogical ideas on the meaningful replenishment of the structural elements of didactic skills of educators showed that the authors consider them without taking into account the changes in the didactic system that occur under the influence of a changing information learning environment. The research of many researchers did not focus on developing the content

of didactic skills associated with new information learning conditions, the state of a changing information learning environment.

METHODS. Didactic preparation of students is a key element of the process of professional formation of the future teacher. Improvement of didactic training of modern students has become a pressing problem of vocational training in a higher institution. The results of the study of modern teaching and practice of special studies have been presented [133; 155; 196], which makes it possible to identify the following characteristics of teaching in an information learning environment:

1) broadening and enhancing the role of students in the types of educational activities carried out on the basis of information and computer technologies, (information activities, Network Information cooperation, modeling of the studied objects, their relations and processes; information formalization, creation of e-learning resource; use of instrumental information systems);

2) change in the ratio of teaching functions without change: information function gradually fall into the fund, giving way to design, design, organization, communication functions, etc.; the educator to some extent remains an engineer;

3) the active acquisition and use of ICT by educators (multimedia presentations, work in virtual laboratories, new media of teaching, e-learning resources, etc.) serves as not only a new tool, but also as didactic conditions that help to formulate competencies that enable students to work in the information environment;

4) the emergence of new structural forms (hypermedia and hypermedia) in the provision of educational materials, the expansion of types of educational-methodical materials (electronic textbooks, electronic tests, instrumental means of modeling educational materials, educational and controlling software tools, etc.).

This makes it possible to identify some of the features of mastering skills in the learning process. For example, it is necessary to create conditions for the active independent activity of students: the formation of qualification is an individual process, which is determined by the individual characteristics of the student, the level and readiness of his development, as well as how the student reacts to this activity, what kind of motivation this activity gives him. In addition, if the student is not a third-party observer, but actively participates in Real professional activity, the formation of didactic skills will be more effective.

Often the formulas of the elements of the didactic system interfere with the achievement of them. In a number of works, the content of didactic skills is determined by the type of activity (evrual activity - mental activity aimed at identifying previously unknown things). Many authors consider the didactic abilities of a modern educator from the point of view of the immutability of the information environment of pedagogical activity.

Some authors (V. A. Krasilnikova [86], L. K. Raikaya [151] and others) although they emphasize the relevance of the influence of information conditions on educational processes, the problem of the formation of didactic skills reflecting the changing capabilities of IOS in future teachers has not been sufficiently developed. Most researchers did not focus on developing the content of didactic skills related to new educational information conditions.

The authors analyzed the current state of didactics and identified four unresolved problems:

- lack of clear, universally defined definitions of basic didactic concepts, such as the learning process, content, teaching methods, forms of learning, subject of learning, etc.;

- lack of clearly expressed and recognized by the didactic community legislation on the educational process;
- excellence in didactic research of methods of natural sciences (observation, experiment);
- didactic research is conducted mainly on the basis of the traditional ("knowledge") approach; personal orientation, competence and lack of adequate study of other approaches.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. The content of interactive techniques and their application. In today's fast-paced time, the most effective way to increase the effectiveness of education is optimal way-to organize classes using interactive techniques the establishment is regarded as. So what are the interval techniques themselves? Partridge what didactic possibilities? Interactive in the educational process, what are the appropriate, purposeful application of the techniques, what guarantees the results?

From a logical point of view, interactivity is, above all, social conversation of subjects (dialogue), action based on interaction, represents the conduct of activities.

The concept of " interactive "in English means"interact" (in Russian derived from the word" интерактив"), from the lexical point of view "inter" – mutual, " act – - means to act, that is, to act among themselves means.

Interactive education –knowledge, skills, qualifications and a certain moral to organize their mutual actions on the way of mastering adjectives based education. Interpersonal-knowledge of participants in the educational process, skills, qualifications and mastering of certain moral qualities Organization of a joint, collaborative action possession of merit.

Every specialist in the field of education is good as far as I know, traditional education is also based on dialogue (dialogue), and this conversation it is organized in the following forms of interaction:

In this case, the Coordination of views in the activities of the student group is based on the situation-communication on the general position in solving educational and professional tasks. Activities were organized with educational texts for better understanding and analysis on the basis of interactive tasks, interactive methods, technologies for the development of critical thinking through reading and writing.

CONCLUSION. Thus, in the process of acquiring didactic skills in the application of Network Interactive means of teaching future teachers, it is necessary to integrate the knowledge gained in mastering the disciplines of the professional cycle in order to organize educational and educational activities of students. This means that it is not enough for the student to study the content of the educational discipline: it is necessary to organize the educational process in order for the future teacher to have special didactic skills.

To do this, at the first stage, the network interactive learning tool should be used as a pedagogical tool and provide students with the solution to their learning tasks. Then the students will be able to develop such an educational tool through the performance of Special Assignments, to understand it as a means of interaction of the subjects of the educational process, which in the future will allow the teachers to develop the ability to use this tool as a didactic tool, that is, the student will be able to use this tool

At the final stage, it is important to formulate didactic skills on the use of a network interactive tool for organizing the educational and educational activities of students, as well as to control and evaluate the performance of their educational tasks.

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